

Heavy metal concentration in precipitation and their impact on the environment

Version 1

Description

This data management plan (DMP) is created for research application No 1.1.1.9/LZP/1/24/141 "Heavy metal concentration in precipitation and their impact on the environment" supported by Activity 1.1.1.9 "Post-doctoral Research" of the Specific Objective 1.1.1 "Strengthening research and innovative capacities and introduction of advanced technologies in the common R&D system" of the European Union's Cohesion Policy Programme for 2021-2027.

Main aims of the project include:

- 1) To perform heavy metal - mercury and indium - concentration monitoring in the rainwater, to assess them as a potential pollution source,
- 2) To perform spectral diagnostics of indium-containing light sources to optimize them for usage in atomic absorption spectroscopy.

Research proposal will be implemented at the Institute of Atomic Physics and Spectroscopy, Faculty of Science and Technology, University of Latvia.

The purpose of the DMP is to outline the strategy for data collection, storing, and sharing at all the stages of research project implementation while ensuring compliance with the legal and ethical requirements.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science | | LCS

Grant

PostDoc Heavy metal concentration in precipitation and their impact on the environment
(1.1.1.9/LZP/1/24/141)

Researchers

Anda Abola (0000-0001-8739-8012)

Organizations

University of Latvia

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [Heavy metal concentration in precipitation and their impact on the environment](#)

Description:

This data management plan (DMP) is created for research application No 1.1.1.9/LZP/1/24/141 "Heavy metal concentration in precipitation and their impact on the environment" supported by Activity 1.1.1.9 "Post-doctoral Research" of the Specific Objective 1.1.1 "Strengthening research and innovative capacities and introduction of advanced technologies in the common R&D system" of the European Union's Cohesion Policy Programme for 2021-2027.

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Organizations:

[University of Latvia](#)

Contact: Abola Anda (anda.abola@lu.lv)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: Latvian Council of Science | | LCS

Grants: PostDoc Heavy metal concentration in precipitation and their impact on the environment (1.1.1.9/LZP/1/24/141)

Project:

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

Publication Date: 2025-10-11

4. Templates

Descriptions

Mercury concentration measurements

Dataset will include experimental data for mercury concentration determination in precipitation obtained by using atomic absorption spectrometer. Samples will be collected in several places in Riga, Latvia and its surroundings.

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Data are collected to analyse mercury content in precipitation (rainwater, snow).

Samples measured are collected in Riga, Latvia and its surroundings during the precipitation episodes (or shortly after, in case of snow and other solid precipitation forms). Measurements are done by atomic absorption spectroscopy.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Experimental data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

CSV

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

200

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

No, I have not considered.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

To scientists analysing mercury pollution data in water, precipitation and similar media.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

Until the publication of the obtained data.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

DataverseLV

<https://dataverse.lv/>

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Standart software tools.

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2027-03-01

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

No

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Anda Abola (0000-0001-8739-8012)

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords
- Physical access control

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

Indium spectral data

In this dataset indium spectral data from high frequency electrodeless light sources will be collected for various applications, such as light source analysis and plasma diagnostics.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

To collect indium spectral data for plasma diagnostics and light sources analysis, for fulfillment of one of the project's main objectives. These will be experimental data registered by spectrometer.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Experimental data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

CSV

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

1

GB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

No, there are no such data available.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

To scientists working in fields of low temperature high frequency plasma

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

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2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

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No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

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2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

Until the publication of the obtained data.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

DataverseLV

<https://dataverse.lv>

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Standart software tools (notepad, R, Python)

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

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Indium concentration data

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Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

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MB

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No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

No, there are no such data available

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

To scientists interested in environmental pollution, indium concentrations in water and other environments.

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